

Church-State-Market Relations in the Context of Indonesia

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The Asian economic crisis that started in 1997 has led to the stepping down of President Suharto who had been in power for 32 years. Since then, the renewal movement, called *Reformasi*, has produced a series of major changes in the political arena. These include amendments to the Constitution which limit the term of office of the president, give more power to the parliament, and make possible direct presidential election. Tight political control by the central government, which characterised Suharto's regime, has been replaced by a decentralisation policy which gives more autonomy to the local governments. Civil society groups, the media and university student unions are now free to express their aspirations.

Despite such important changes toward democracy in the political arena, the economic recovery is very slow. One reason for this stagnancy is the failure of the new governments to reduce corruption, which has been so widespread since Suharto's era. A recent survey by Transparency International shows Indonesia as the most corrupt country in Asia, and the sixth in the world. Such a finding does not surprise the Indonesian people, since corruption has become

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a daily experience in almost all public services provided by the government and state-owned companies. Both the quantity and the quality of corruption in Indonesia seem to be immune to *Reformasi*.

Corruption has so much to do with political relations. In Indonesia, the major parties making up the corrupt political relations are the political circle - including those in the government, the parliament and the court - and the business actors. The nature of the relations is patron-client, in which the political party provides protection or access to the government projects, and the business party 'appreciates' that by giving the political figures honorary executive and/or shareholding positions or just a lump-sum commission. Most major holding companies in Indonesia are involved in such patron-client relationships. In the case of small and medium scale businesses, a simpler form of corruption, bribery, is necessary for the firms to obtain licences, permits and other required documents. They also have to 'maintain good relationship' with the local rulers if their business has to operate in a 'conducive environment.'

Economically speaking, patron-client relationships result in market distortion and high-cost economy. The distortion of the Indonesian market discourages foreign investments to respond positively to the government programme of attracting more capitals. High-cost economy makes Indonesian products uncompetitive, hampering Indonesian industries to take advantage of the regional free market zone. Patron-client relationships also cost a significant portion of the state budget, which should be allocated for social welfare. Also, the involvement of the government officials in patron-client relationships contributes much to the impotence of the state in protecting the public interests when they conflict with those of the client.

The effect of the patron-client relationship upon the development of democracy is obviously negative, since it strengthens the power of a given regime regardless of its performance. This can make a bad regime work unchallenged, driving the country into a terrible situation. In other words, the prevalence of the patron-client relationship has kept the Indonesian market away from a democratic economic system. Moreover, as Eugene Tan observes,¹ such a relationship enhances anti-Chinese sentiments already existing among the dominant ethnic groups in Indonesia, particularly when the economic condition is not good.

Given such a crucial position of the issue of corruption in the contexts of Indonesian economy and politics, a theological-ethical reflection regarding political relations in Indonesia should include a serious look at that issue.

The Apolitical Tendency of the Business Actors

The practice of patron-client relationships between state officials and business actors in Indonesia has both political and cultural roots. One factor fostering the construction of such relationships is the tendency of the business party to take an apolitical position. Such a tendency is related to the fact that a significant portion of the Indonesian business sector is practically run by the ethnic Chinese.

Chinese-Indonesians have a political reason for being apolitical. From the Dutch colonial to post-Suharto period, governments treated this ethnic group with ambivalent policies: on the one hand some governments acknowledged the expertise of the ethnic Chinese in business, and therefore allowed them, and sometimes even supported them, to play a prominent role in the market; on the other hand, some other governments employed discriminatory policies to prevent the ethnic Chinese from developing a political interest. Given such ambivalent policies, Chinese-Indonesians have been politically paralysed. In such a condition, economically effective but politically crippled, they were made a perfect client for the rulers who were seeking a good economic reputation, whilst suspicious of anyone or any groups with political ambition.

In addition to the political reason, cultural factors also contribute to the apolitical tendency of the ethnic Chinese. Cultural factors are concerned with the tradition of building a network based on personal relationship within Chinese business communities. The network, known as '*guanxi*' serves as an economic as well as a moral system, which overcomes 'the problems of contract uncertainty' resulting from the weak and/or corrupt judicial institutions.² The patron-client relationship, on the part of the ethnic Chinese, is the 'political *guanxi*' needed in order to secure their position, which is always threatened by discrimination and poor legal system.³ Despite the fact that the traditional socio-cultural *guanxi* has been an inspiration of the political *guanxi*, the latter operates with a different set of values. Whilst trust and solidarity are crucial values in the social-cultural *guanxi*, those values are absent in the political *guanxi*, since both parties only make use of each other.

According to Wrong Siu-lun, who observes the relationship between the ethnic Chinese business community and the state in Hong Kong and Singapore, the apolitical tendency of the ethnic Chinese is rooted in the Confucian concept of social hierarchy, which places merchants in a politically low position, whilst rulers are in the prestigious one.⁴ Zhang Wei-bin contends that such social hierarchy implies a perfect vision of a free-market society, in which business people should concentrate on business matters and let the rulers do the politics.⁵ Zhang thus neglects the socio-psychological aspect, such that the hierarchy creates a feeling of political inferiority on the part of the business people, which makes them vulnerable to political abuse.

The Relevance of Existing Political Theological Approaches

Political issues have long been important subjects in theological discourses. Different approaches to the matter of political relations have been suggested. Since each approach basically responds to a particular political situation, its relevance to a different social context should be critically considered. In this paper I will examine the theological approaches which influence the activities and practices of the Church in Indonesia in dealing with political issues. I will particularly focus on pietism, chaplaincy and liberationist approaches.

Pietism Approach

Christian pietism was a forceful spirituality behind the evangelisation movement which initiated church-plantation in the colonised Indonesia. Its emphasis on the salvation of the human soul and the holiness of personal life made it pay very little attention to political ethics. This explains the relatively uncritical relationship between the western missionaries and the colonial government which made possible the sending of the former to the colony. It was the work of those missionaries which led to the formation of most Indonesian Protestant denominations, which are divided along geographical and ethnic lines. In this case, Chinese-Indonesian churches are rather exceptions. For most of them were not planted by western missionaries, but were rather the fruits of the works of individual ethnic Chinese, whose conversion to Christianity had been a result of their spiritual enquiry. Nevertheless, the growth of those churches owed much to the revival movement brought to Indonesia by Chinese preachers coming from the USA and China with a strong spirit of pietism.⁶ Among those preachers were John Sung and Dzao Tze Kwang, whose revival

ministries in Java in the 1939 brought a significant number of ethnic Chinese into Christian faith.

Given that historical background, it is not surprising that pietism is still influential among Indonesian Christians. Although many Indonesian theological scholars have tried to develop theological approaches responding specifically to actual political affairs, they often find it uneasy to compete with the tendency towards pietism strongly planted in the minds of common church members. Such a tendency is even enhanced by the fast growth of contemporary evangelicalism and Charismatic movement among Indonesian Christians. Although some evangelical groups have recently showed an interest in political issues, particularly after the *Reformasi*, their focus tends to be narrowly directed to the struggle for the political rights of the Christian communities themselves, such as the right to build churches. On wider political issues, they tend to hold either an ignorant or opportunistic attitude.

In the case of the Chinese-Indonesian Christian business community, Christian pietism matches the Chinese cultural trait of being apolitical. As a result there is a sort of spirituality which lays much emphasis on personal and family ethics, but avoids the area of political ethics. The popularity of groups such as the Full Gospel Business Men's Fellowship and the Bethany Successful Family among Chinese-Indonesian Christians indicate the persistence of pietism in this community. It goes without saying that corruption issues, such as that involving patron-client relationships, are outside the coverage of such groups' moral messages.

Pietism is a sort of spirituality the Suharto's regime preferred to approve. Notably in the early part of his leadership era, he worked hard silencing Islamic groups who tended to be politically critical. Warning the people to be cautious of any extreme ideologies, he named politically-critical Islamic groups 'the right extreme' as a pair of his latent enemy, 'the left extreme': the Communist. Meanwhile, suspecting politically-critical Christians for being an ally of 'the left extreme,' Suharto's government banned theological books discussing political issues, such as those on liberation theology.

In Suharto's era, evangelisation movements based on Christian pietism successfully converted a significant number of ethnic Chinese business people

to Christianity. This can be seen in the vast emergence of new urban churches with evangelical or charismatic style. By embracing Christianity, those business people found a new community, and perhaps a new standard of morality in terms of personal and familial matters. Yet, they retained their apolitical position concerning the political dimension of their business practices. Their conversions, thus, had little impact on their involvement in the patron-client relationships.

Chaplaincy Approach

The history of the Church includes times when political ethics was neglected, but also times when the concern about it was significant. As Scottish theologian, Duncan Forrester⁷ notes, the early Church did not think it necessary to reflect on political ethics, since it was expecting an immediate coming of the new age to replace the existing world with its political structure. Only at a later stage that such a necessity was considered inevitable. The Church's later awareness of the need to play a political role led to the emergence of 'Christendom.' For Forrester, Christendom 'meant the definitive entry of Christianity into public realm, there to fulfil functions unthought of in the early days of the church.'⁸ It was during the Christendom period that the Church began the chaplaincy approach: seeing the politically powerful as an object of pastoral work. Although the chaplaincy approach in the Christendom era was often distorted by practices of inappropriate collaboration between the Church leaders and the rulers, it demonstrates a serious attempt to infuse Christian principles in the political arena. The chaplaincy approach at that time tried 'to seek in the Gospel guidance for rulers and to regulate the political and economic systems with criteria agreeable to the Christian faith.'⁹

A modern version of the chaplaincy approach is based on the idea of the national church. The Church of England is an obvious example. In this case, the chaplaincy approach does not merely take the form of providing religious ceremonial assistance to the government, as often accused. In fact, it often offers critical advice pointing out the inconsistency of government policies with Christian ethics. An example of such advice is a research-based document titled 'Faith in the City' issued by the Church of England, which is a critical response to the British government's public policies concerning 'urban priority areas.' Despite hostile reactions expressed by part of the government as well as the press and the academics,¹⁰ the document is clearly qualified as a pastoral statement addressed to the policy makers.

In Indonesia, the chaplaincy approach can be seen in the work of theologians commending the state ideology *Pancasila*,¹¹ and exploring development issues in the times of Suharto. Most prominent leaders of the Communion of Churches in Indonesia in those times fall under the category of such theologians. Basically those leaders emphasise the importance of *Pancasila*, not particularly for the protection of the Christian community, but for the continuing existence of the modern nation of Indonesia. For instance, T.B. Simatupang, a former army general turned church leader, urges Christians to subscribe to *Pancasila* wholeheartedly. He believes that there is no contradiction between *Pancasila* and the Christian faith. Rather, the relations between the two can be synergistic: Christians should be inspired and motivated by their faith to participate in the life of the nation according to the norms embedded in *Pancasila*.¹² Simatupang's insistence is reasserted by Eka Darmaputera, who wrote his PhD dissertation in Boston College on *Pancasila*. Referring to Simatupang, Darmaputera¹³ believes that *Pancasila* is the only option for Indonesia to maintain its unity and plurality. It is the result of the Indonesian people's search for a modern identity by exploring their cultural potentials. He argues that any attempt to replace *Pancasila* either with a concept of an Islamic state or else would put the existence of the nation at stake.

Echoing the claim repeatedly stated by Suharto, those theologians believe that the government's programme of development is and should remain 'an implementation of *Pancasila*.' For them, the task of political theology is to ensure that the government does its job of implementing *Pancasila* in 'a pure and consequent way.' At the same time, the call of the Church is to participate in development so long as it is an implementation of *Pancasila*. Compared to the Church of England's 'Faith in the City,' the Indonesian theology of development is, in fact, much softer.

The chaplaincy approach is a step forward from the position held by pietism. Its contribution to the development of western politics is significant, as Forrester notes. In the context of Indonesia, however, the effectiveness of such an approach is more limited. Being in a minority position, the Church, and, therefore also, Christian theologians have less opportunity to play the role of political chaplain than their western counterparts do. The Indonesian theology of development also tends to accommodate only the aspiration of the church elite, and, therefore, its relevance for daily business practice is hardly seen.

Liberationist Approach

A strong criticism of the theology of development comes particularly from theologians who are inspired by liberation theology. For those liberationists, the theology of development neglects the real problem of development, which is more ideological than practical. Liberationists point to the capitalist orientation of the concept of development as its fundamental problem. With such an orientation, development can only benefit the upper middle class and large capital owners at the expense of the life of the poor. They contend that the idea of development as an implementation of *Pancasila* is only a tool of the hegemonic power of the government to control critical voices within society which represent the interest of the poor.¹⁴

The liberationist approach refers to the 'prophetic trajectory' in the Old Testament political perspectives. As John W. de Gruchy notes,¹⁵ the prophetic trajectory emphasises the act of Yahweh as the liberating God, who sets the people free from slavery, and calls them into a covenant with Godself. Social justice, concern for the poor and the oppressed, and life within community, therefore, are major themes in the prophetic trajectory. De Gruchy argues that the Jesus movement is on track of that trajectory as demonstrated in Jesus' own emphasis on the coming of the reign of God, with its socio-political implications.

It is obviously crucial for the Church to support the liberationist approach's consistent concern for the poor. For it is ultimately the poor who are mostly victimised by the practices of patron-client relationship and other forms of corruption so prevalent in Indonesia. In the case of the politically-crippled ethnic Chinese business actors, the liberationist approach could be interpreted as a call to realise their political dignity, and therefore to repent from the apolitical position. It thus provides an alternative for both pietism and the Confucian concept of social hierarchy, which have contributed to the shaping of political inferiority feeling of those business people.

However, the liberationists' hostility to the market economy is hard to be accepted as an encouraging signal by the business community, whose survival depends heavily on the existence of the market. For it is only in the context of the market that those people's excellent record is historically proven. Moreover, the liberationists' single emphasis on the poor tends to offer an over-pessimistic

valuation of those who are not included in the category of the total poor. The economic condition of the business people would certainly disqualify them from being included in the total poor category. In relation to those holding decision-making positions in the government, the liberationist approach is also hard to gain a sympathetic response, given its tendency to offer a radical structural and systemic change as the only hope. As Forrester notes, liberationists tend to be too suspicious to realise that there are political decision-makers in the existing government who are facing 'the dilemmas and ambiguities involved in the responsible use of power,'¹⁶ and thus in need of a practical assistance rather than an ideological repentance.

Partnership: An Alternative Approach

Pietism leaves the patron-client relationship in an area outside its coverage. Chaplaincy approach fails to recognise the capacity of the Church to play a realistic role in solving the problem of that relationship. Liberationists focus on the victims of such relationship, but offer little hope for the parties involved in it. What is the alternative?

Learning from the Experience of the Muslim

Islam does not share the idea of separating religion and politics. For Muslims, faith always has a political dimension. A position similar to that of Christian pietism, therefore, is not common among the Muslim community. Along Indonesian history, different Islamic groups have attempted different political approaches. As the majority religion, Islam has every chance of being the chaplain of the state. The chaplaincy approach is indeed practised at all levels of government institutions. The existence of the Councils of Clerics is a clear example of such an approach. Those institutions, however, tend not only to be elitist, but also to limit their interests exclusively to the issues affecting the Muslim community.

Another important approach is the radical one. The radical approach tries to change the western-style secular system with an explicitly Islamic one, either by means of violence or a constitutional way. Its spirit is similar to that of the liberationist, despite their differences in ideological orientation and strategy. Despite its persistent struggle in Indonesian history, the radical approach fails to attract the support of the people. In the recent General Election, political parties employing the radical approach lost a significant number of votes. Whether the existing political condition is satisfying or not, the Indonesian people

have traumatic experiences of ideological confrontation. An idea of radical systemic and ideological changes, therefore, is not very popular.

A more sympathetic approach from the side of the Muslim is coming from moderate groups. Its orientation is directed to the common good of the whole people, not limited to the Muslim community itself. The moderate camp is critical of many practices of the government, promotes commitment to democratic values, but avoids practical-political intervention. Rejecting the idea of the radical group about changing the political system with the Islamic one, the moderate is open to partnership, dialogue and cooperation with other parts of society, including other religious communities.

The Age of Partnership

John Atherton¹⁷ explores the ways the Christian community has played important roles in political histories, particularly in Britain. He identifies 3 periods, in each of which a particular approach is employed by the Christian community. The first period was the early industrialisation era, marked by a *laissez faire* understanding of the market. In that period, the Christian community's dominant approach was represented by the 'evangelical nonconformity,' which promoted not only the individual virtues of honesty, diligence, and conscience, but also the spirit of volunteerism leading to the formation of voluntary organisations and civil society groups. In the second period, which was 'the age of the state,' marked by the giving to the state more roles in welfare affairs, the Christian community responded with the theology of incarnation, leading to the formation of the Christian socialist tradition.

Atherton argues that since 1960s we are entering a new period, which is 'the age of partnership.' The marks of this age are plurality and diversity found in almost all societies in the world. In this period, there is no longer 'one grand narrative in politics, religion, or economics (that) can describe or explain (the present situation) satisfactorily.'¹⁸ Consequently, partnerships involving sectors of society and between sources of thoughts are crucial for responding to the present situation.

Although reflecting particularly the context of Britain, Atherton's analysis is inspiring. For plurality and diversity have marked Indonesian society from the outset, and are now even enhanced by the process of globalisation. It has also

become evident that the recovery from the economic collapse of the country and political reformation toward democracy cannot be left to a single sector of society, be it the state, voluntary bodies, or a religious community. This is also implicitly acknowledged in the moderate Muslim camp's openness to partnership. It is thus relevant to talk about political relations in terms of partnership involving religious, political as well as market institutions. In this case, I would suggest the following considerations.

Firstly, it is more realistic to develop church-state-market relations in the context of inter-religious partnership. An inter-religious team would represent a wider portion of society and thus be taken into account than what a single religious body could achieve. It would thus solve the problem of incapacity found in the chaplaincy approach. An inter-religious partnership might find problems related to doctrinal differences. Yet, inter-religious dialogues, research and studies in Indonesia have been quite successful in finding consensus and common ground for many ethical issues.

Secondly, the involvement of an inter-religious team in church-market relations would be powerful enough to challenge the patron-client nature of the relations, and to call for a new kind of partnership with a more constructive orientation toward the common good of the whole society. An inter-religious team would be capable of providing political-ethical resources for overcoming the problem of political inferiority feelings of the business people, which, as described above, have become a crucial factor in the making of the patron-client relations.

¹ Eugene Kheng-Boon Tan, 'Success Amidst Prejudice: Guanxi network in Chinese businesses in Indonesia and Malaysia.' *Journal of Asian Business*, 16:1 (2000), 76.

² Janet T. Landa, 'The political economy of the ethnically homogenous Chinese middleman group in Southeast Asia: Ethnicity and entrepreneurship in a plural society' in Linda Y.C. Li and Peter L.A. Gostling (eds.) *The Chinese in Southeast Asia, vol. 1: Ethnicity and Economic Activity*. Singapore: Maruzen Asia, 1983.

³ Eugene Kheng-Boon Tan, 'Success Amidst Prejudice: Guanxi network in Chinese businesses in Indonesia and Malaysia, p. 70.

⁴ Wong Siu-lun, 'Business networks, cultural values and the state in Hong Kong and Singapore in Rajeswary Ampalavanar Brown (ed.), *Chinese Business Enterprise in Asia*. London: Routledge, 1995, p. 145.

⁵ Zhang, Wei-bin, *Confucianism and Modernization: Industrialization and Democratization in the Confucian Regions*. London: Macmillan Press, 1999, pp. 77-78.

- ⁶ See: Chris Hartono, *Orang Tionghoa dan Pekabaran Injil*, Yogyakarta: TPK, 1996, p. 77-81.
- ⁷ Duncan Forrester, *Theology and Politics*, Oxford: Basil Blackwell, 1988.
- ⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 28.
- ⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 29.
- ¹⁰ Regarding 'Faith in the City,' see: Nigel Biggar, *Theological Politics*, Oxford: Latimer House, 1988, also Anthony Harvey (ed.) *Theology in the City: A Theological Response to 'Faith in the City'*, London: SPCK, 1989.
- ¹¹ *Pancasila* (The Five Principles) covers both democratic principles implied in western-like secularism and the most basic religious interest, which is belief in the One God, without a reference to a particular religion.
- ¹² T.B. Simatupang, *Imran Kristen dan Pancasila*. Jakarta: BPK Gunung Mulia, 1985, p. 206.
- ¹³ Eka Damaputera, *Pancasila: Identitas dan Modernitas, Tinjauan Etis dan Budaya*, p. 130.
- ¹⁴ For criticism of Simatupang's theology of development from a liberationist perspective, see: Julianus Mojau, 'Teologi politis T.B. Simatupang: Sebuah telaah kritis,' in *Jurnal Teologi Gema*, 54, 2004, pp. 107-126.
- ¹⁵ See: John W. de Gruchy, *Christianity and Democracy: A Theology for a Just World Order*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1995, pp. 40-48.
- ¹⁶ Duncan Forrester, *Theology and Politics*, p. 105.
- ¹⁷ John Atherton, *Public Theology for Changing Times*, London: SPCK, 2000, pp. 72-83.
- ¹⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 84.

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